

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part VIII. Synthesis of Some New 3-Methyl-5-(*p*-methoxy/ethoxyphenyl)-4-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles as Potential Antibacterials

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1-(*p*-Methoxy/ethoxyphenyl)-3-methyl-2-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones on condensation with three carbonyl reagents yield the corresponding 3-methyl-5-(*p*-methoxyethoxyphenyl)-4-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles. These azole derivatives on screening were found to exhibit considerable activity against *S. aureus*.

IN continuation of our earlier work¹⁻⁴ on the synthesis and screening of pyrazole derivatives, this paper describes the preparation of 3-methyl-5-aryl-4-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles (I) in order to study the effect of exchange of an electron withdrawing group by an electron repelling one from the phenyl ring at position-5 of the nucleus on the antibacterial activity. The compounds were synthesised by condensing 1-(*p*-methoxy/ethoxyphenyl)-3-methyl-2-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine and thiosemicarbazide; the homogeneity and purity of these compounds were tested through T.L.C. The yields in all the cases were good and ranged between 69 to 80%.

Experimental

1-Aryl-3-methyl-2-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones required for this work were obtained according to the procedure already described⁵.

Synthesis of 1-thiocarbamido-3-methyl-5-(p-methoxyethoxyphenyl)-4-(N-substituted p-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles.

Thiosemicarbazide (0.05 g.) was added to a solution of appropriate 2-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-dione (0.1 g) in glacial acetic and ethanol mixture, followed by the addition of a small amount of sodium acetate and few drops of water. The reaction mixture was refluxed in a water bath for 7-8 hr; after keeping the contents overnight, the deposited solid was filtered, dried and crystallised.

Cyclisation reactions with hydrazine hydrate (100%) and phenylhydrazine were carried out following the procedure described in earlier communications.³⁻⁴

Antibacterial activity

On the basis of the work on biological assay it is clear that majority of the pyrazole derivatives exhibit considerable activity against *S. aureus* and either no or very feeble activity against *E. coli*. The pyrazoles having the methoxyl group in the phenyl ring attached at position-5 were found to be more active as compared to those having the ethoxyl group. Another conclusion drawn has been that the pyrazole derivatives having the heterocyclic ring in the sulphonamide moiety exhibit greater activity and out of these the one having the 5-methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl ring were found to be the most active. On comparing these results with those obtained earlier, it is evident that introduction of an alkoxy group causes an overall increase in activity thereby lending further support to our earlier observations.

TABLE 1—3-METHYL-5-(*p*-METHOXYPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

(Ar = *p*-methoxyphenyl ; R₁ = H)

S. No	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
					<i>S. aureus</i> ,	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	238	RO	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₄ S	(+)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	240	O	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ S	(++)	(+)
3.	Phenyl	220	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	223	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₄ S	(+)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	221	RO	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₄ S	(+)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	205	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₄ S	(++)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	320	RO	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₅ S	(+)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	225	O	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	260	YO	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ S	(+)	(-)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	247	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	235	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxy-pyrimidyl	235	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	270	R	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₇ S ₂	(++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	236	O	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₄ S	(+)	(+)

TABLE 2—1-PHENYL-3-METHYL-5-(*p*-METHOXYPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

(Ar = *p*-methoxyphenyl ; R₁ = phenyl)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
					<i>S. aureus</i> ,	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	235	B	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	230	R	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	218	R	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	214	R	C ₃₃ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	200	R	C ₃₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₅ S	(-)	(+)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	185	R	C ₃₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	194	Y	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	227	R	C ₃₈ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	285	R	C ₃₇ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₇ S	(++)	(-)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	183	B	C ₃₉ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	230	R	C ₃₉ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₇ S	(++)	(-)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxy-pyrimidyl	205	R	C ₄₁ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₇ S	(++)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	190	B	C ₃₆ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₇ S ₂	(++++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	230	R	C ₃₈ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)

TABLE 3—1-THIOCARBAMIDO-3-METHYL-5-(*p*-METHOXYPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

(Ar = *p*-methoxyphenyl ; R₁ = thiocarbamido)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial & activity	
					<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	234	R	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	230	R	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(-)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	217	BR	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	215	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(-)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	219	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(-)	(+)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	205	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	315	R	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(+)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	227	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₇ S ₂	(+)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	267	R	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(++)	(-)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	245	R	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(+)	(-)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	250	YB	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(++)	(-)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxy-pyrimidyl	275	O	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S ₂	(++)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	241	R	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(++++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	232	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	(+)	(+)

TABLE 4—3-METHYL-5-(*p*-ETHOXYPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENE AZO) PYRAZOLES

 (Ar = *p*-ethoxyphenyl ; R₁ = H)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
					<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	242	OY	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₅ S	(-)	(++)
2.	Acetyl	245	OY	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	225	R	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	(+)	(+)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	233	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₅ S	(+)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	220	OR	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₅ S	(+)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	216	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	302	O	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	263	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	255	O	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	222	YO	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₇ S	(+)	(+)
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	220	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₇ S	(++)	(+)
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	232	OY	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₇ S	(++)	(+)
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	282	Y	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₇ S ₂	(+++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	230	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)

 TABLE 5—1-PHENYL-3-METHYL-5-(*p*-ETHOXYPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENE AZO) PYRAZOLES

 (Ar = *p*-ethoxyphenyl ; R₁ = phenyl)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
					<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	200	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	195	O	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₅ S	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	178	O	C ₃₀ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	190	O	C ₃₁ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₅ S	(+)	(-)
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	160	O	C ₃₁ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
6.	Guanidyl	156	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
7.	α -Pyridyl	205	O	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
8.	Pyrimidyl	185	O	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
9.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	215	O	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
10.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	140	O	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₅ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
11.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	142	O	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₇ S ₂	(++++)	(+)
12.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	247	O	C ₂₉ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)

 TABLE 6—1-THIOCARBAMIDO-3-METHYL-5-(*p*-ETHOXYPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENE AZO) PYRAZOLES

 (Ar = *p*-ethoxyphenyl ; R₁ = Thiocarbamido)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
					<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	240	O	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	238	OR	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	227	R	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	188	Y	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(+)	(-)
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	212	O	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(-)	(-)
6.	Guanidyl	300	O	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₈ S ₂	(+)	(-)
7.	α -Pyridyl	260	R	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₇ S ₂	(+)	(-)
8.	Pyrimidyl	261	YO	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₈ S ₂	(-)	(-)
9.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	215	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₈ S ₂	(-)	(-)
10.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	252	OR	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₈ S ₂	(-)	(-)
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	225	R	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₈ S ₂	(+)	(-)
12.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	280	YO	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₈ S ₂	(++++)	(+)
13.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	242	YO	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	(-)	(-)

B = Brown ; Br = Brownish ; O = Orange ; R = Red ; Y = Yellow

All the synthesised compounds gave satisfactory analysis for C and H.

References

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